

Impact of Improvised Materials on Creative-Thinking–Abstractness of Title in Basic Science among Secondary School Students in Makurdi, Benue State

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Abstract

This study determined impact of improvised materials on creative-thinking –abstractness of title in basic science among secondary school students in Makurdi, Benue state. A pre-test post-test quasi-experimental-control group research design was used adopted for the study. The study was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. The study’s population was made up of 1337(680 male and 657 female) Upper Basic two (JSS II) government secondary school students during the 2021/2022) academic session. A multistage sample of 52 (23 male and 29 female) students in two intact classes from two schools was drawn. Torrance Test of Creative Thinking with a reliability coefficient of 0.82 determined by a test-retest method with Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used for data collection. Data were analysed using mean and two-way ANCOVA. Findings showed no significant difference in creative-thinking abstractness of titles among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material, $F_{(2,45)} = 1.641$; $p = .205 > .05$. Although, there existed a significant difference in creative-thinking abstractness of titles in favour of those taught using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material, $F_{(1, 45)} = 42.733$; $p = .000 < .05$, no significant difference existed in the students’ creative-thinking abstractness of titles based on gender, $F_{(2, 17)} = .982$; $p = .395 > .05$. Therefore, it was concluded that, enhancing creative-thinking abstractness of titles among students with different abilities can be achieved without any gender discrepancy by actively involving learners in the improvisation of instructional materials. Thus, teacher-learner improvisation approach was recommended for teaching Basic Science in basic schools.

Keywords: Teacher-Learner Improvised Material (TLIM), Teacher Improvised Material (TIM), Creative-Thinking Abstractness of Titles, Diverse-Ability and Gender.

Introduction

In the rapidly evolving landscape of the 21st century, creativity has emerged as a fundamental driving force behind innovation, problem-solving, and progress across various domains. As technology advances, economies globalize, and societies become more interconnected, the ability to think creatively and adaptively has become indispensable (Alfiyah, Sunyono & Andra, 2022; Dianita, 2023). Creativity transcends traditional boundaries, enabling individuals to envision novel solutions to complex challenges, sparking artistic expressions that resonate with diverse audiences, and fostering a culture of continuous growth and exploration (Long, Balakrishnan, Yan & Chiet, 2020; Nazhifah, Wiyono, Ismet & Azairok 2023). In a world defined by constant change, nurturing and harnessing creativity is not just a luxury; it is an essential skill that empowers individuals and societies to thrive in the face of unprecedented opportunities and uncertainties. In the dynamic landscape of the current age, the realm of science education stands at a crossroads, poised to adapt and innovate in response to the rapidly emerging challenges that our world presents. As technological breakthroughs, environmental shifts, and complex societal issues redefine the boundaries of scientific inquiry, fostering creativity within science education has never been more critical (Trisnayanti,

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Ashadi, Sunarno, & Masykuri, 2020; Oliveira, Brown, Su, Zhang, LeBrun, Eaton & Yemen, 2021). To equip the next generation with the tools they need to address these challenges head-on, science education must embrace and prioritize creativity as an integral component, enabling students to not only comprehend the intricacies of scientific principles, but also to wield their creativity in shaping a sustainable, innovative, and adaptive future.

Creativity is our capacity to find new solutions to the problems we encounter by using our existing knowledge. Creativity is an act arising out of a perception of the environment that acknowledges a certain disequilibrium, resulting in productive activity that challenges patterned thought processes and norms, and gives rise to something new in the form of a physical object or even a mental or an emotional construct (Balci, Baykal, Göksun, Kisbu & Yantaç, 2023; Apaydin, 2023). Creativity thus implies the act of turning new and imaginative ideas into reality. In our age, where information is developing and changing very rapidly, societies need individuals who are proactive, thinking creative, problem-solving, and constantly improving them in order to adapt to this change and development (Apaydin, 2023). Therefore, this infers that in order to confirm a sustainable development, the creativity potential of the individuals who create the society must be continuously improved by innovative approaches which will engender creativity skills such as creative thinking. Creative thinking refers to the ability to generate diverse and numerous responses to a particular issue that increases the likely output of creative ideas (He & Wong, 2021; Aldossari, 2021). According to Ayua, Terhemba, Omega and Samuel (2023) creative thinking is one's cognitive process to generate effective ideas in solving problems under certain aims and conditions. Creative thinking abilities hold immense value for nations, researchers, educators, and workplaces alike, driving their efforts to enhance creativity through innovative teaching. In line with this, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) in her National Policy on Education emphasizes the exposure of learners to Basic Science concepts to develop skills and knowledge necessary for meeting contemporary societal needs. One of the principal objectives of Basic Science education is to foster learners' creative thinking ability, facilitated by effective teaching/learning materials. Nevertheless, the National Teachers' Institute - NTI (as cited in Ikyernum, Ayua & Terhemba, 2022) noted that the materials for science teaching are lacking and thus compelling teachers to improvise.

Improvisation refers to making provision for something not readily available. It is the process by which educational materials are locally made to meet the purpose of the realia (Ayua, Ikyernum & Terhemba, 2022). To teach science at the basic school level, having sufficient teaching aids is key to making teaching-learning processes more engaging and interesting. Improvisation according to Ayua (2021) could be by substitution, modification and construction either solely by the teacher (Teacher Improvised Material) or by the combined efforts of the teacher and learners (Teacher Learner Improvised Material). Teacher Improvised Material (TIM) refers to teaching aid(s) made by the teacher alone and brought to the classroom for Basic Science teaching. TIM is an improvisation approach that is teacher-based because learners are not involved in the process of producing the improvised instructional material(s) (Ikyernum, Ayua & Terhemba, 2022). Teacher-Learner Improvised Material (TLIM) on the other hand refers to teaching aids that are collaboratively produced by both the teacher and the learners for the purpose of Basic Science teaching and learning (Ikyernum, Ayua & Terhemba, 2022). This approach emphasizes the active involvement of both the teacher and the students in creating these materials. By adopting a teacher-learner-based improvisation method, students gain essential knowledge about the subject matter and are encouraged to think creatively even before the actual lessons take place. This process fosters a more engaging and interactive learning environment, allowing students to actively participate in their education and take ownership of their learning experiences. In the realm of effective Basic Science education, two pivotal concepts come to the forefront: creative thinking and improvisation. These concepts hold immense significance in crafting, selecting, and utilizing appropriate instructional materials, particularly in regions where production technology is still evolving (Ikyernum, Ayua & Terhemba, 2022). The integration of improvisation into the teaching and learning process is increasingly acknowledged as a means to cultivate and amplify creative thinking among students (Navarro, 2018). Fostering creative thinking through improvisation not only equips students with vital skills for societal success but also contributes to economic advancement in our technology-driven 21st-century world. Consequently, prioritizing the cultivation of creative thinking and improvisation within educational contexts becomes imperative. Creative thinking comprises five sub domains of fluency, originality, elaboration, resistance to premature closure and abstractness of titles (Tehemba, Ayua & Gamat, 2023). Nonetheless, this paper focused on creative-thinking abstractness of titles.

Creative-thinking abstractness of titles is the ability of learners to synthesise and organise processes of thinking, capture the essence of information involved, know what is important and produce good titles (Chua, Balakrishnan, Choong, & Koh, 2020). Creative-thinking abstractness of titles is the degree beyond concrete labelling or physical description of the picture drawn which relates to the respondents' ability in synthesising and organising processes of thinking (Ng & Lee, 2019; Hahm, Kim & Park, 2019; Chua, Balakrishnan, Koh & Chiet 2020). Creative-thinking abstractness of titles is a vital aspect of creative thinking as it plays a crucial role in fostering valuable ideas which equips individuals with the essential competencies needed

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to thrive in modern societies driven by creativity. Özgenel, Canpolat, Yağan and Canlı (2019) in their study “the effects of enriched workshop training given to pre-school students on creative thinking skills of students” found that there was a significant increase in creative thinking abstractness of titles after students were exposed to the enriched training to foster creative thinking. Likewise, Ng and Lee (2019) in their study “assessment of creative thinking of Hong Kong undergraduate students using the Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking” found that learners’ creative-thinking abstractness of titles was well above average. In contrast Chua, Balakrishnan, Choong and Koh (2020) and Chua, Balakrishnan, Koh and Chiet (2020) in their respective studies on creative thinking established that there was no significant improvement in the creative thinking abstractness of titles after learners were exposed to the creative thinking module. Though the studies assessed the creative-thinking abstractness to titles of learners, they however were not concerned with creative-thinking abstractness of titles as an aspect of creative thinking in relation to improvisation across diverse-ability learners.

In this research, the term "diverse-ability" refers to the different educational performance levels of students in Basic Science, which can be categorized as high, average, or low based on their past academic scores. Maikano (as cited in Ikyernum, Ayua & Terhema, 2022) maintained that ability grouping is determined by educators' assessments of students' abilities. When assigning students to different tracks, their prior test scores or performance measures from previous grades are considered to determine their ability levels. Students' ability levels for this study were guided by Benue State Ministry of Education – BSME (2021) and Benue State Examinations Board – BSEB (2019) grading system for basic schools. Based on the grading system, High Ability Level (A = 75-100% and B = 65-74%), Average Ability Level (C = 55-64% and D = 45-54%) and Low Ability Level (E = 40-44% and F = 0-39%). By using this grading system, the researchers were able to distinguish and group students based on their academic ability levels in Basic Science. Ikyernum, Ayua and Terhema (2022) in their study “Effect of teacher-learner improvised material on creative thinking among diverse-ability upper basic science students in Makurdi metropolis” established that the level of creative thinking among diverse-ability students was significantly enhanced without gender disparity as a result of learners’ active involvement in the improvisation of instructional materials. However, Balci, Baykal, Gökşun, Kisbu and Yantaç (2023) in their study “My Creative World (MCW): Improving Creative Thinking in Elementary School-Aged Children” found that there was no significant treatment effect of creative thinking abstractness of titles after learners were exposed to the creativity intervention programme. These studies however were not concerned with creative-thinking abstractness of titles in relation to improvisation and did not tell whether a difference existed in creative-thinking abstractness of titles based on gender as a result of learners’ involvement in improvisation of instructional materials.

Gender differences encompass the characteristics associated with being male or female, man or woman, boy or girl. Research by Danjuma (as cited in Ayua, 2021) indicates that these gender disparities have a worldwide impact, particularly in Africa, by hindering the equal participation of boys and girls in Science Education. Consequently, these gender-specific factors influence the teaching, learning, and creative thinking of students in Basic Science. Empirically, Ulger and Morsunbul (2017); Zhang, Ren and Deng (2020), in their respective studies on differences in creative thinking found that a significant difference existed in creative thinking abilities between males and females in favour of females. However, Ayua and Agbidye (2020); He and Wong (2021); Ayua, Terhema and Ikyernum (2022) and Midilli, Özsoy, Aslan (2022) found no significant difference between boys and girls in the level of entrepreneurial creativity, divergent thinking and problem-solving skills, creative thinking, and creative-thinking abstractness of titles respectively. However, none of the studies were concerned with creative-thinking abstractness of titles as an aspect of creative thinking in relation to improvisation. That is why determining creative-thinking abstractness of titles among upper basic science students using improvisation is imperative. The problem of this study is that, the modern world has undergone significant paradigm shifts. These changes, attribute to the knowledge revolution and rapid technological advancements, highlight the importance of creativity skills in an ever-evolving world. To effectively navigate this dynamic environment, educational strategies need be realigned to match these transformative trends with anchorage at basic education for cultivating creative-thinking. Although, improvisation is a common term in education, the extent to which it may aid creative-thinking abstractness of titles among upper basic science students remains a subject that requires deeper exploration. Hence, the need for this study.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were:

1. To determine the Creative-Thinking Abstractness of Titles (CTAT) scores of students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material (TLIM) and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material (TIM)
2. To find out the CTAT scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using TLIM based on gender.

Research Questions

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The study had two questions:

1. What is the mean difference in CTAT scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using TLIM and those taught using TIM?
2. What is the mean difference in CTAT scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using TLIM based on gender?

Hypotheses

The null hypotheses for the study were:

1. There is no significant difference in CTAT scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using TLIM and those taught using TIM.
2. There is no significant difference in CTAT scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using TLIM based on gender.

Methodology

A pre-test post-test quasi-experimental-control group design was used for this study. After pre-test administration, the experimental group of an intact class of 1:24 was taught concept of work, energy and power with 5 lesson plans using demonstration method blended with Teacher-Learner-Improvised Materials (wooden toy car and wooden electric fan) constructed through active involvement of learners together with the teacher using procedures outlined in the lesson plans; while the control group was taught the same concept using same method blended with Teacher-Improvised Materials. This treatment lasted for five weeks. Thereafter, the students in both groups were given post-test. Students diverse-ability were based on previous term’s performance grades (high = A/B; average = C/D; low = E/F). A multistage sample of 52 (23 male and 29 females?) Upper-Basic II students in two schools drawn from the population of 1337 (680 males and 657 females) Upper Basic II students in all the 21 secondary schools during the 2021/2022 academic session (Teaching Service Board Makurdi, 2021) was used for the study. Torrance Test of Creative Thinking (TTCT-Figural B) was used for data collection. Section “A” collected students’ biodata; while section ‘B’ had three activities each lasting for 10 minutes with the opportunity for multiple responses of ideas, to test students’ creative-thinking abstractness of titles in Basic Science. TTCT-Figural B was validated and trial-tested with a reliability coefficient of 0.82 determined by a test-retest method with Pearson Product Moment Correlation. Extraneous variables like group initial difference, group interaction effect and priming were controlled by homogeneity test, distant locations and impromptu tests respectively. Both pre-test and post-test were administered under standard examination conditions. The research questions were answered using mean and hypotheses were tested at 0.05 α -level using a two-way Analysis of covariance due to normality of the distribution, homogeneity of variance, randomness of selection, measurement based on interval scale and independence of samples.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean difference in creative-thinking abstractness of titles scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material?

Table 1: Mean and Standard deviation of creative-thinking abstractness of titles scores of students taught using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material and Teacher Improvised Material.

Ability Level	N	Group	Pre-TTCT		Post-TTCT		Mean Gain	Mean Gain difference
			$\bar{x}$	SD	$\bar{x}$	SD		
High	12	TIM	1.77	0.615	1.96	0.392	0.19	2.15
	10	TLIM	1.70	0.327	4.04	1.265	2.34	
Average	8	TIM	1.58	0.493	1.71	0.476	0.13	1.31
	7	TLIM	1.46	0.113	2.90	0.829	1.44	
Low	8	TIM	1.55	0.414	1.59	0.181	0.04	1.75
	7	TLIM	1.64	0.395	3.43	1.449	1.79	
Cluster		TIM	1.63		1.75		0.12	

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TLIM 1.60 3.46 1.85 1.74

Table 1 shows homogeneity in the pre-test mean scores among diverse-ability between experimental and control group with cluster means of 1.63 and 1.60. The table also shows that creative-thinking abstractness of titles mean scores among diverse-ability in the experimental group were higher than those in the control group with cluster mean gain difference of 1.74.

Research Question 2

What is the mean difference in creative-thinking abstractness of titles scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material based on gender?

Table 2: Mean and Standard deviation of Creative-Thinking Abstractness of Titles Scores of students taught using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material based on gender

Ability Level	Gender	N	Pre-TTCT		Post-TTCT		Mean Gain	Mean Gain Difference
			$\bar{x}$	SD	$\bar{x}$	SD		
High	Male	7	1.80	0.252	3.83	0.969	2.03	0.03
	Female	3	1.47	0.416	3.53	0.966	2.06	
Average	Male	2	1.50	0.000	3.30	0.707	1.80	0.78
	Female	5	1.44	0.134	2.46	0.808	1.02	
Low	Male	2	1.50	0.000	3.30	0.707	1.80	0.15
	Female	5	1.67	0.427	3.62	1.491	1.95	
Cluster	Male		1.60		3.48		1.88	0.21
	Female		1.53		3.20		1.67	

Table 3 shows homogeneity in the pre-test mean scores between male and female in the experimental group with cluster means of 1.60 and 1.53. Likewise, the table also shows that the creative-thinking abstractness of titles mean scores in the post-test was higher than those in the pre-test in both male and female with cluster mean gains of 1.88 and 1.67 respectively

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in creative-thinking abstractness of titles scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material and those taught using Teacher Improvised Material.

Table 3: Summary of Two-way ANCOVA Results of Creative-Thinking Abstractness of Titles Test Scores of Students Based on Improvisation Technique

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	45.001 ^a	6	7.500	9.754	.000	.565
Intercept	27.627	1	27.627	35.929	.000	.444
Pre-TTCT	.022	1	.022	.029	.865	.001
Improvisation	32.860	1	32.860	42.733	.000	.487
Diverse-ability	5.859	2	2.929	3.810	.030	.145
Improvisation* Diverse-ability	2.523	2	1.261	1.641	.205	.068
Error	34.602	45	.769			
Total	420.800	52				
Corrected Total	79.603	51				

a. R Squared = .565 (Adjusted R Squared = .507)

Table 2 shows no significant difference in the creative-thinking abstractness of titles scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using TIM and those taught using TLIM, $F_{(2, 45)} = 1.641$; $p = .205 > .05$. The null hypothesis was therefore not rejected. However, the result also showed that students' creative-thinking abstractness of titles scores in the experimental group was better than those in the control group, $F_{(1, 45)} = 42.733$; $p = .000 < .05$. This implies that, although Teacher-Learner Improvised Material (TLIM) enhances creative-thinking abstractness of titles, it is not dependent on students'

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academic abilities.

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference in creative-thinking abstractness of titles scores among diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material based on gender.

Table 4. Summary of Two-way ANCOVA Results of Creative-Thinking Abstractness of Titles Scores of Students Taught Using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material Based on Gender

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	11.336 ^a	6	1.889	1.181	.362	.294
Intercept	4.522	1	4.522	2.827	.111	.143
Pre-TTCT-TLIM	.388	1	.388	.242	.629	.014
Gender	.701	1	.701	.438	.517	.025
Diverse-ability-TLIM	6.221	2	3.111	1.945	.174	.186
Gender *	3.142	2	1.571	.982	.395	.104
Diverse-ability-TLIM						
Error	27.194	17	1.600			
Total	327.650	24				
Corrected Total	38.530	23				

a. R Squared = .294 (Adjusted R Squared = .045)

Table 4 showed no significant difference in the creative-thinking abstractness of titles scores between male and female diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material, $F_{(2, 17)} = .982$; $p = .395 > .05$. The null hypothesis was therefore not rejected. This implies that, Teacher-Learner Improvised Material is gender unbiased; hence it enhanced creative-thinking abstractness of titles in both male and female diverse-ability Basic Science students.

Discussion of Findings

Concerning students' creative-thinking abstractness of titles based on their involvement in the improvisation of instructional materials, it was found that significant difference existed in creative- abstractness of titles between students in the control and experimental groups in favour of those in the experimental group. However, among the ability levels there existed no significant difference in creative-thinking abstractness of titles. Following field experience, the finding of this study is not odd because during the construction process, students were given ample opportunity to fully synthesise and organise processes of thinking, capture the essence of information involved, know what is important and produce good titles which thus entail creative-thinking abstractness of titles. This finding is similar with Özgenel, Canpolat, Yağan and Canlı (2019) who found that there was a significant increase in creative-thinking abstractness of titles after students were exposed to the enriched training to foster creative thinking. The finding also agrees with that of Ng & Lee (2019) who established that learners' creative-thinking abstractness of titles was well above average. However, the finding does not only contrast with, but is a potential solution to those of Chua, Balakrishnan, Choong and Koh (2020), Chua, Balakrishnan, Koh and Chiet (2020) and Balci, Baykal, Gökşun, Kisbu and Yantaç (2023) who found no significant improvement in the creative thinking abstractness of titles after learners were exposed to creative thinking enhancement programmes. The indifference among diverse-ability students in creative-thinking abstractness of titles as found out, is similar to Ikyernum, Ayua and Terhemba (2022) findings of no significant difference in creative thinking among diverse-ability students.

Regarding students' creative-thinking abstractness of titles based on gender, it was discovered that no significant difference existed in creative-thinking abstractness of titles between male and female diverse-ability students taught Basic Science using Teacher-Learner Improvised Material. Thus, involving students in the improvisation of instructional materials to enhance their creative-thinking abstractness of titles is gender unbiased. This finding is similar to those of Ayua and Agbidye (2020); He and Wong (2021); Ayua, Terhemba and Ikyernum (2022) and Midilli, Özsoy, Aslan (2022) who found no significant difference between boys and girls in the level of entrepreneurial creativity, divergent thinking and problem-solving skills, creative thinking, and creative-thinking abstractness of titles respectively. This finding however does not only differ but also is solution to Ulger and Morsunbul (2017), Zhang, Ren and Deng (2020) who found out that a significant difference existed between females and males upon creative thinking in favour of females.

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Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that: Creative-thinking abstractness of titles among diverse-ability students can be enhanced without gender discrepancy if learners are actively involved in the improvisation of instructional materials.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made to effectively implement this approach:

1. Teacher-Learner Improvisation approach should be adopted in teaching Basic Science.
2. School administrators should encourage researchers to organize workshops on the use of Teacher-Learner Improvisation.
3. Ministries of Education and teacher training institutions in Nigeria should ensure in-service training and retraining of teachers on Teacher-Learner Improvisation.
4. School proprietors, heads and parents' teachers' association should materially/financially support Teacher-Learner Improvisation in Basic Science.

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